

20

22

ANNUAL
REPORT

Let's make life better

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FEMaLe 2022

Highlights

January

CES 2022: SurgAR

FEMaLe partner promotion #1

[Interview playlist on YouTube](#)

National endometriosis action plan, France

In early January 2022, the French President, Emmanuel Macron, launched the first Action Plan to Fight Endometriosis. [Source](#) (Youtube)

February

FEMaLe partner promotion #2

[Interview playlist on YouTube](#)

Webinar/panel: Young people in the media

[View the webinar on YouTube](#)

FEMaLe partner promotion #3

[Interview playlist on YouTube](#)

ESHRE guidelines

[Find the PDF via this link](#)

Podcast: #unheardof

With Nilüfer we discuss the genetic risk factors for endometriosis, and learn more about the COHERE project; one which aims to understand endometriosis amongst women in Northern Cyprus. Finally, Ulrik tells us about the FEMaLe project; one that aims to use machine learning to better understand, diagnose and treat endometriosis.

[Listen to the podcast here](#)

TIEF on television in Hungary

March

FEMaLe-WHO awareness campaign

FEMaLe + ENDO.DK awareness campaign

Transnational partner meeting

FEMaLe partner promotion #4

[Interview playlist on YouTube](#)

TIEF - Feme, Live with endometriosis

April

FEMaLe partner promotion #5

[Interview playlist on YouTube](#)

Tam Dalyell public lecture

Profs Philippa Saunders and Andrew Horne are determined to find new ways to tackle endometriosis.

In 2022 they shared the The University of Edinburgh's Tam Dalyell Prize for Excellence in Engaging the Public with Science.

The Conversation (Canada) article

[You can read the article here](#)

Peer reviewed article #1

[Link to article](#)

FEMaLe partner promotion #6

[Interview on YouTube](#)

May

Webinar: EEL / ESHRE Guidelines

FEMaLe partner promotion #7

[Interview on YouTube](#)

PrecisionLife named Analytics Company of the Year at the British Data Awards

LADYWALK

June

..... FEMaLe partner promotion #8

[Interview on YouTube](#)

..... Congress: EEL 6th Congress

FEMaLers Ulrik and Adrienn + Endometriosis.UK's president, Emma Cox

National Action Plan for Endometriosis in Denmark

[Read Ulrik's LinkedIn post](#)

July

..... Lessons from implementing the Australian National Action Plan for Endometriosis

[Read our LinkedIn post about it here](#)

..... 28 days later podcast

India explores period pain with Dr Katy Vincent, we meet Phoebe who lives with endometriosis and discusses the condition and hopes for a cure with Dr Andrew Horne.

[Link to the podcast](#)

August

- FEMaLe adviser promotion #1, Oral
[Interview on YouTube](#)

- FEMaLe project study reveals major under-diagnosis of widespread women's disease
[Link to press release](#)

- FEMaLe adviser promotion #2, Tomlinson
[Interview on YouTube](#)

September

- Partner promotion #9 Correlate
[Interview on YouTube](#)

- FEMaLe adviser promotion #2, Nap
[Interview on YouTube](#)

●... EGI Conference Workshop

●... 1st FEMaLe Project review

[Read Ulrik's post on LinkedIn](#)

●... Partner promotion #10 KTH

[Interview on YouTube](#)

October

●... ECSA - European Citizen Science Association's Conference in Berlin, Germany

[Link to our post on LinkedIn](#)

- Joint FEMaLe TRANSFORM webinar on First-person experiences of endometriosis. Participatory research, needs and recommendations of people with endometriosis [Webinar on YouTube](#)

ECREA Conference Aarhus
 Adviser Maria Tomlinson and Ulrik with our collaborative poster

- FEMaLe adviser promotion #4, Kvaskoff [Interview on YouTube](#)

November

Partner promotion #11 Semmelweis
[Interview on YouTube](#)

- Instagram LIVE & webinar with Endometriosis.uk

December

FEMaLer Mette Nyegaard visits Australia's Grant Montgomery

[Read our post on LinkedIn](#)

Interview with Irina Verwer

[Interview on YouTube](#)

M1-M18

Work Package achievements

Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 1:
IMPACT

FEMaLe
findmyandrometriois.eu

Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 2:
CODE

FEMaLe
findmyandrometriois.eu

Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 3:
PHENOTYPE

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 4:
OMICS

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 5:
BIG DATA

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 6:
DIAGNOSIS

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 7:
VISUAL

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 8:
DIGITAL

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 9:
BEACON

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Month 1-18 achievements

Work Package 10:
GOVERNANCE

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WORK PACKAGE

ACHIEVEMENTS / SUMMARY

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WP1 IMPACT

To support impact monitoring and assessment throughout the project, we have co-produced impact cases and conducted constructive evaluation interviews per work package. A total of 18 impact cases and 18 follow-up interviews have been completed to track KPIs, planned events, and progress.

WP2 CODE

We have provided a comprehensive framework to secure that FEMaLe's activities and results are aligned with the European Union's idea of an inclusive, innovative, and reflective society. To improve FEMaLe's impact on ethics, gender, inclusion, and open science, we have participated in workshops and at conferences as well as recruited ten advisers and professionals, including researchers, those with endometriosis, activists etc.

WP3 PHENOTYPE

We have developed and completed a baseline questionnaire and reached consensus on the most relevant symptoms to identify people with endometriosis.

We have published our first study, a register-based study on the prevalence, incidence and geographical distribution of hospital diagnosed endometriosis in Denmark.

<https://obgyn.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/aogs.14364>

WP4 OMICS

We have set up a pipeline that involves discovery of high-risk genotype combinations, replication of genotype combinations and computation of risk scores for endometriosis.

WP5 BIG DATA

The Lucy app can be used to monitor self-reported endometriosis, mental health, physical activity, and environmental factors to classify any behavioural patterns underlying clinical manifestations in people with endometriosis related to stress and infertility issues and nutritional and other lifestyle factors. The Lucy App is available in Hungarian, English, Danish, and Swedish:

<https://hellolucy.app/en>

We have co-developed the Lucy Questionnaire and started collecting data from users, which will help us to develop patient profiles and structured clinical data. This is not only relevant to Lucy App users, but it will have a significant impact on the classification of new patterns of endometriosis.

WORK PACKAGE

ACHIEVEMENTS / SUMMARY

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WP6 DIAGNOSIS

We have reached consensus and confirmed an annotation pipeline by using the Delphi method, selecting the 'bounding boxes' method, which is the first step in developing a computer vision tool that automatically will confirm the diagnosis and assessment of the different endometriosis lesions.

WP7 VISUAL

Legal agreement has been established with Hungary (Semmelweis University Hospital), France (Clermont-Ferrand University Hospital) and Brazil (Beneficência Portuguesa). So far, 129 surgeries have been collected, 289 short video sequences extracted, and 42,814 endometriosis lesions totally annotated.

WP8 DIGITAL

We have developed MY ENDO, an online mindfulness- and acceptance-based endometriosis management program in 10 online modules, including 25 yoga exercises and three yoga series. We have conducted a feasibility pilot test of the first four modules of the program, which have guided specific improvements of and refinements to the original program.

WP9 BEACON

We have achieved a total organic reach of 2,501,582 views, mainly due to communication campaigns (41%), popularized publications (24%), social media activities (21%), public events (7%), and the FEMaLe website and newsletters (5%).

We have established FEMaLe on social media, in particular LinkedIn (427 followers), Twitter (1,148 followers), Instagram (335 followers), and YouTube.

We have launched the FEMaLe website: <https://findingendometriosis.eu/> where you can sign up for the FEMaLe newsletter at the bottom of the page!

WP10 GOVERNANCE

We have utilized the Half Double Methodology – a state-of-the-art hybrid project management framework – to reduce time to impact, keep the project in motion and promote the leadership of people (FEMaLers). Leadership has been embracing uncertainty and being capable of handling unexpected changes by uniting all the different points of view and created a shared commitment to the common vision.

We have set up Correlate FEMaLe as our dedicated knowledge management platform to support communication and collaboration, which can integrate seamlessly with other FEMaLe tools to optimize the flow of knowledge.

FEMaLe SoMe metrics

Performance on Social Media

2022 in numbers

484 POSTS
509.915 REACHED
1.054 AVG. REACH / POST
17.229 REACTIONS
36 AVG. REACTIONS / POST

LINKEDIN

725 FOLLOWERS
154 POSTS
4.856 REACTIONS
32 AVG. REACTONS / POST
251.592 VIEWS
1.634 AVG. VIEWS / POST

TWITTER

1249 FOLLOWERS
216 POSTS
10.627 REACTIONS
49 AVG. REACTIONS / POST
227.295 IMPRESSIONS
1.052 AVG. IMPRESSIONS / POST

INSTAGRAM

435 FOLLOWERS
114 POSTS
1.746 REACTIONS
15 AVG. REACTONS / POST
31.028 EXPOSURES
272 AVG. EXPOSURES / POST

THANK YOU VERY MUCH FOR 2022!

If you haven't done so already, please follow FEMaLe on social media and interact with us and the united endometriosis community!

*click the icons to start to
engage already today!*

Let's make life better